

**SYNTHESIS IN THE ALLOXAZINE, ISOALLOXAZINE
(FLAVIN) AND LUMAZINE GROUPS. PART I.
SYNTHESIS OF 6- OR 7-PHENYL AND
6:7-DIPHENYLLUMAZINES,**

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In connection with the investigations on the chemootherapy of tuberculosis, the author required a group of compounds which can stain the tubercle bacilli and also possess some specific properties so that their metallic salts can be used for intraperitoneal injections. Compounds of the alloxazine (Ia) and isoalloxazine (Ib) groups, the ring structure of which has recently been shown by Kuhn, Karrer and others to be present in vitamin B₂ (lactoflavin), possess most of the requisite properties (*cf.* Kuhn and Boulanger, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1936, 241, 233). A series of synthetic attempts have, therefore, been launched with a view to synthesise compounds of these groups, with suitable substituents in the benzene ring, which are expected to possess some specific bactericidal effects.

Attempts in introducing particular substituents *e.g.*, I, OH, OR, SH, SR, etc., in the benzene ring of alloxazine or isoalloxazine according to the current methods of Kuhn (*Ber.*, 1934, 67, 1459 and following papers; Kühling, *Ber.*, 1891, 24, 2363) or Karrer (*Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1934, 17, 1516, and following papers) were attended with working difficulties, since either the requisite substituted diamines were not easily accessible or the corresponding *orthonitro*halogen compounds could not be employed. The synthesis of some derivatives of lumazine (II, Kuhn and Cook, *Ber.*, 1937, 70, 761), with substituents in positions 6 or 7 or both, was next undertaken with a view (a) to test whether the phenyl-substituted compounds possess properties (physical and physiological) similar to the alloxazines and (b) to elucidate whether the particular properties of the alloxazines are due only to the lumazine residue itself.

(Ia)

(Ib)

Sachs and Meyerheim (*Ber.*, 1908, **41**, 3965) condensed 3-methyl-4:5-diaminouracil and also 1:3-dimethyl-4:5-diaminouracil with diacetyl, pyruvic acid and mesoxalic acid and obtained the corresponding lumazine derivatives. Very recently Kuhn and Cook (*loc. cit.*) have obtained the corresponding lumazine derivatives by condensing 4:5-diaminouracil sulphate with diacetyl-glyoxal (polymer), methylglyoxal, β -naphthoquinone and phenanthrenequinone. Some more new compounds of the above type have now been prepared by condensing 4:5-diaminouracil sulphate with phenyl-substituted 1:2-diketones.

Phenylglyoxal hydrate ("Organic Synthesis", XV, p. 67) was found to condense with 4:5-diaminouracil sulphate to give 6- or 7-phenyllumazine (III or IV), resembling alloxazine in its physical properties. The work on the condensation of various derivatives of phenylglyoxal with 4:5-diaminouracil sulphate as also with 4:5-diaminothiouracil is nearing completion and will shortly be communicated.

Benzil condenses with 4:5-diaminouracil sulphate furnishing 6:7-diphenyllumazine (V).

The condensation of 4:5-diaminouracil with a series of mono- and di-substituted benzils did not proceed smoothly; whereas 3:3'-diiodo-, 4:4'-diiodo-, 4:4'-dimethoxy-, 3:3'-dimethoxy-, and 4-methoxy- benzils appear to yield only traces of products in unworkable yields and benzpiperil did not at all undergo condensation. In the case of the hydroxybenzils, besides bad yields, the working up of the products offered additional difficulties.

Piperil appears to yield the corresponding 6:7-di-(3:4-methylenedioxyphenyl)-lumazine (VI) in bad yield.

Unsuccessful attempts were made to condense phenylglyoxaloxime, benzilmonoxime and piperil monoxime with 4-aminouracil to obtain the corresponding lumazines (III or IV), (V) and (VI). Though phenanthrenequinone condenses with 4:5-diaminouracil sulphate to give the corresponding 9':10'-phenanthrolumazine in very good yield, all attempts to condense phenanthrenequinonemonoxime and 4-aminouracil under a variety of conditions ended in failure.

This and the other allied instances clearly show that although the hydrogen atom in position 5 in 4-aminouracil is reactive, yet it does not react with the hydroxyl of the oxime group.

The study of the condensation of 4:5-diaminouracil with the various benzils indicates that the substituents in the benzene ring modify the reactivity of the carbonyl groups to a great extent. With a view to find out the individual influences of the various substituents, the condensations with several benzils are being tried. It is quite interesting to note that all the benzils (excepting some 2:2'-disubstituted compounds) give the corresponding quinoxaline derivatives with *o*-phenylenediamine (though the dioximes are formed only with difficulty in some cases) which makes it evident that the amino groups in 4:5-diaminouracil are not so reactive as those in *o*-phenylenediamine. It is also significant that phenanthrenequinone condenses with 4:5-diaminouracil quite readily to yield the lumazine in quantitative yields, whereas benzil does not condense so readily and the yield is not so good.

As a preliminary to the study of similar condensations with the 1:2-diketones of the terpene series camphorquinone has been condensed with 4:5-diaminouracil sulphate to yield 2':3'-camphorolumazine, which can be represented either by (VII) or (VIII).

(VII)

(VIII)

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

4:5-Diaminouracil Sulphate.—This compound was prepared according to the directions of Kuhn and Cook (*loc cit.*) and also by the rapid method of Bogert and Davidson (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, **55**, 1667). While the former method directly gave a purer product, the latter method gave a better yield and is most suited for large scale preparations, since the conversion of cyanoacetylurea into 4-aminouracil according to the first method could not be effected satisfactorily in quantities more than 4 or 5 g. at a time.

6- or 7-Phenylumzine.—In the preparation of phenylglyoxal hydrate, after refluxing acetophenone with selenium dioxide in alcohol for 3 hours, the solvent was removed first under ordinary and then under reduced pressure, and the resulting thick oil being freed from selenium by careful filtration or better by centrifuging, was dissolved in the minimum quantity of boiling water and filtered. On cooling the filtrate, phenylglyoxal hydrate separated in a crystalline form.

A mixture of phenylglyoxal hydrate (0.6 g), 4:5-diaminouracil sulphate (1.0 g.), glacial acetic acid (25 c.c.) and water (175 c.c.) was gently refluxed for 40 minutes when the condensation product separated from the clear solution. After cooling, it was filtered (yield, 0.5 g.) and recrystallised from dilute alcohol when it was obtained as glistening red needles not melting up to 330°. (Found: N, 22.96. C₁₂H₈O₂N₄)

requires N, 28.33 per cent). Some more of the product could be obtained from the mother liquors on concentration. A dilute alkaline solution of this lumazine shows a green fluorescence.

The dimethyl derivative of the above lumazine was prepared as follows : To the finely powdered lumazine (0.3 g.) was added an ice-cold ethereal solution (40 c.c.) of diazomethane obtained from 1.5 g. of nitrosomethylurea and the mixture allowed to stand for about 20 hours, first few hours being in ice-cold water and then at the room temperature. The ether was removed by distillation and the resulting product crystallised from formic acid. After three crystallisations the methyl derivative was obtained as yellow needles or prisms, m.p. 278°. (Found : N, 21.20. $C_{14}H_{12}O_2N_4$ requires N, 20.89 per cent).

6:7-Diphenylbenzil.—When a mixture of benzil and 4:5-diaminouracil sulphate was refluxed in glacial acetic acid for 1 hour, the yield of the lumazine was not found to be good. By prolonging the heating for 5-8 hours, the yield was improved and it was considerably improved by the addition of a little boric acid (Kuhn). The following condition has been found to be the best :

A mixture of benzil (0.5 g.), 4:5-diaminouracil sulphate (0.5 g.), water (100 c.c.) and glacial acetic acid (50 c.c.) with a little boric acid was refluxed for 5 hours and on cooling the solution a mixture of some unchanged benzil and 6:7-diphenylumazine separated, which was collected. The former can be freed from the condensation product either by washing the mixture thoroughly with carbon tetrachloride or by shaking it with dilute sodium hydroxide, filtering and acidifying the filtrate (yield, 0.38 g.). On recrystallisation from dilute acetic acid, it was obtained as colourless shining crystals, m.p. 310-315° depending upon the rate of heating. (Found : N, 17.45. $C_{19}H_{14}O_2N_4$ requires N, 17.72 per cent). It dissolves in dilute sodium hydroxide forming a light yellow solution which shows a green fluorescence.

Piperil.—Piperonyloin was prepared by Perkin (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1891, 59, 164) and in trying to oxidise it to piperil by nitric acid he could not obtain piperil. Biltz and Wienands (*Annalen*, 1899, 308, 11), however, oxidised it by boiling it in an alkaline solution. This method was not found to be satisfactory in working with large quantities. The following method gave a good yield.

A mixture of piperonal (30 g.), ethyl alcohol (80 c.c.), water (20 c.c.) and sodium cyanide (8 g.) was refluxed on the steam-bath for 1½ hours, a further quantity of sodium cyanide (5 g.) added and the mixture refluxed for 1½ hours more. It was allowed to stand at the room temperature till the

liquid at the bottom completely solidified. The filtered product was carefully washed with dilute caustic soda and sodium bisulphite solution and finally with water and dried, yield 27 g. A mixture of finely powdered copper sulphate (42 g.), pyridine (40 c.c.) and water (16 c.c.) was heated on the steam-bath with shaking and to the clear solution, piperonyloin (25 g.) was added and heating continued with good shaking for 2½-3 hours. After cooling, the solution was diluted, filtered and the piperil, thoroughly washed free from the copper salt, was obtained as fine yellow prisms. Since it is somewhat sparingly soluble in alcohol, it can also be purified by boiling it with a little alcohol twice and filtering. The product thus obtained melted at 170-71°.

Action of Piperil on 4:5-Diaminouracil Sulphate.—The condensation of piperil with diaminouracil sulphate was tried by boiling equimolecular quantities of the components in a solution of (i) glacial acetic acid for 2-12 hours, and also in the presence of boric acid and (ii) dimethylaniline. By working up in the usual way, a small quantity of a yellow product was obtained, which showed fluorescence in alkaline solution. It crystallised from a large volume of boiling water, not melting up to 330°. (Found : N, 13.72. $C_{20}H_{12}O_6N_4$ requires N, 13.35 per cent).

2':3'-Camphorolumazine.—A solution of camphorquinone (0.8 g.) and diaminouracil sulphate (1.1 g.) in water (125 c.c.) and glacial acetic acid (50 c.c.) was heated under reflux for about 1 hour. Since nothing separated on cooling the solution was concentrated to a small volume, diluted a little with water and after standing, the separated crystalline product was filtered off. The product was treated with dilute sodium hydroxide and on acidifying the filtrate, the lumazine separated in a crystalline form. It was collected by filtration and crystallised from dilute acetic acid as yellow prisms, not melting up to 320°. (Found : N, 19.96. $C_{14}H_{16}O_2N_4$ requires N, 20.58 per cent). It shows fluorescence in dilute alkaline solution.

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